

Cyclisation of 4-(1'-anthraquinonylamino) Benzanthrone

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Manuscript received 28 July 1975; accepted 14 May 1976

Cyclisation of 4-(1'-anthraquinonylamino) benzanthrone with sulphuric or polyphosphoric acid yields an orange dye. Its constitution has been elucidated in the present work. Analysis of the dye indicates that it is formed by cyclodehydration. Oxidation, reduction with aluminium isopropoxide and reductive acetylation studies indicate its structure as (IV). The mechanism of its formation involving a carbonium ion intermediate is suggested.

4-(1'-anthraquinonylamino) Benzanthrone (I) can be prepared by two methods: (a) condensation of 4-chlorobenzanthrone (IIa) with 1-aminoanthraquinone (III) under Ullmann's conditions¹; (b) reaction of benzanthrone (II) with 1-aminoanthraquinone using dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) and potassium hydroxide². The latter method is the recent one and is preferable as 4-chlorobenzanthrone is difficultly accessible. The constitution of the product from the second reaction is based on the fact that 4-anilinobenzanthrone together with a small amount of 6-anilinobenzanthrone is obtained if aniline is used in place of 1-aminoanthraquinone³.

Cyclisation of (I) with sulphuric acid has been stated to yield an orange dye¹, the constitution of which is not known. In the present work, the orange dye could be obtained by reaction with sulphuric acid as well as by polyphosphoric acid. Analysis of the pure product indicated that it was obtained by cyclodehydration of (I) rather than by cyclodehydrogenation. Ring closure can take place at 3- or 5- position of benzanthrone. Benzanthrone substitutes in 3-position in an electrophilic substitution⁴. However, nitration of 4-hydroxy- and 4-acetamidobenzanthrones takes place in the 5- position⁵. This indicates that ring closure should be at 5- position rather than 3- position. A six membered ring is formed if the ring closure takes place at 5-position as against a seven membered ring if the ring closure takes place at the 3- position. The first compound would be aromatic and stable and would exhibit vatting and dyeing properties, while the second compound will not exhibit the above properties. So the dye can be assigned the structure (IV).

The above conclusions were supported by the oxidation studies, where both the parent compound and the dye gave the same oxidation product (V). It appears that cyclisation took place during the oxidation of (I). Reductive acetylation and reduction with aluminium isopropoxide gave (VI) and (VII). This also confirmed the above conclusion.

Its mechanism of formation may be visualised as shown in the Scheme.

Arnesen and Langmyhr⁶ examined solutions of 1,1'-dianthrimide (VIII) in sulphuric acid conductometrically and concluded that one molecule of anthrimide takes up three protons, the -NH group protonating first. Hence the first step is the protonation of nitrogen to yield (IX). This is tautomeric with the structure (X), involving addition of proton to the carbonyl oxygen followed by the electrophilic ring closure by the resulting positively charged carbon to yield (XI). Dehydration and subsequent loss of proton yield (XII) and (IV) respectively.

The spectral characteristics of (I) and (IV) may be compared with those of (XIII) and (XIV).

Compound	λ max in H ₂ SO ₄ in nm.	C=O region — ir — C—C stretch 1630–1670 cm ⁻¹ — 1400–1590
(XIII)	255, 360, 315, 430, 510–540.	1667, 1640 1505, 1590
(I)	232, 255, 278, 314, 375, 462, 538.	1628, 1660 1568, 1590.
(XIV)	244, 275, 388, 456, 568, 608.	1670 1525, 1545, 1570.
(IV)	238, 268, 332, 588, 578.	1668 1538, 1568, 1590.

Anthraquinonylaminobenzanthrones absorb near 255, 375, and 540 nm; while their dehydrative cyclisation products absorb at 388 nm and exhibit a much stronger band at longer wavelengths. In the carbonyl region (XIII) and (I) show two strong bands at 1630–1670 cm⁻¹, the cyclised products (XIV) and (IV) show one band in the C=O region in i.r. This observation is in agreement with the differentiation of cyclised and uncyclised anthrimides by spectral characteristics by Venkataraman⁷. In the C—C stretch region, the cyclised products show more bands than the corresponding uncyclised products. This is in agreement with the differentiation by spectral characteristics by Shah⁸.

I

II, (R=H)
a, (R=Cl)

III

IV

V

VI

VII

VIII

Cyclisation of (I) with alkali is stated to yield a black dye⁹. However, in the present experiments, alkaline cyclisation in ethylene glycol gave mainly 4-hydroxybenzanthrone and only traces of the dye which could not be worked up further.

Experimental

4-(1'-anthraquinonylamino)Benzanthrone (I)

Benzanthrone (from Atic Industries, Bulsar, India) (3 g.), 1-aminoanthraquinone, purified by chromatography on alumina in *o*-dichlorobenzene, (2 g.), powdered potassium hydroxide (9 g.) and dimethyl sulphoxide (25 ml.) were stirred at room temperature for 6 hr. The red brown product (3 g.) was collected after diluting it with water containing hydrochloric acid. The solution of the red brown product in

nitrobenzene was chromatographed at 130° on alumina, and the chromatogram was developed with the same solvent. It separated into 5 fractions. The first and the second least adsorbed minor fractions were of unreacted benzanthrone and 1-aminoanthraquinone respectively. The third major brownish red band was eluted with pure nitrobenzene. On concentration, it gave red brown plates, not melting upto 300°. Crystallisation of the product from nitrobenzene gave red brown plates which analysed for (I). (Found : C, 82.6; H, 3.9; N, 3.2%. Calc. for C₃₁H₁₇NO₃, C, 82.5; H, 3.8; N, 3.1%. λ_{max} in sulphuric acid at 232, 255, 278, 314, 375, 462 and 538 nm. Infra red at 1660 and 1628 cm⁻¹ in the C=O region and 1568 and 1590 cm⁻¹ in the C-C stretch region). It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid to a violet solution.

Cyclisation of (I)

(a) Orthophosphoric acid (60 ml) was added to phosphorus pentoxide (90 g.) at 0° in 30 min, and the mixture was gradually heated to 100° and maintained at the same temperature for 1 hr. The above substance (3 g.) was added to the mixture and the mixture was stirred for 6 hr. at 145°–155°; the colour of the mixture changed from red to pink. The mixture was then poured into water and the precipitate was collected. The solution of the product in *o*-dichlorobenzene was chromatographed on alumina and the chromatogram was developed with the same solvent. It separated into two fractions. The first weakly adsorbed major orange red fraction was eluted with pure *o*-dichlorobenzene. On concentration, it gave orange needles not melting upto 300°. Crystallisation from *o*-dichlorobenzene gave orange needles which analysed for IV. (Found : C, 85.6; H, 3.5; N, 3.0%. Calc. for C₃₁H₁₅NO₃; C, 85.9; H, 3.5; N, 3.0%. λ_{max} in sulphuric acid

at 238, 268, 332, 388, and 518 nm. Infra red at 1668 cm⁻¹ in the C=O region and 1538, 1568, and 1590 cm⁻¹ in the C–C stretch region.)

It dyed cotton orange from orange red vat. The orange red vat turned green on boiling. It dissolved in sulphuric acid with brown red colour.

(b) (I) (0.5 g.) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (20 ml) and nitrobenzene (5 ml.) was added to it. The solution was kept for 3 days at room temperature. A red orange precipitate was collected after diluting it with water. On working up further, as per the above procedure, it gave the product (IV) with same analytical and spectral characteristics as mentioned above.

Oxidation of (IV)

(IV) (2 g.) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (40 ml) and the mixture was refluxed. To this was added, chromium trioxide (8 g.) in water (40 ml) and acetic acid (60 ml) dropwise. The mixture was refluxed for 5 hr more and then diluted with water (3 l) and kept overnight. The yellow product which separated was collected (0.5 g.). It was washed with water till neutral to Congo Red paper. It was strongly adsorbed on alumina in chromatography in *o*-dichlorobenzene and could not be eluted. Crystallisation from *o*-dichlorobenzene gave yellow plates, which analysed for the formula V. (Found : C, 76.2; H, 3.2; N, 3.0%. Calc. for C₂₉H₁₃NO₅; C, 76.5; H, 2.9; N, 3.1%). It dissolved in alkaline dithionite to a red vat but did not dye cotton. Its solution in concentrated sulphuric acid was yellow.

Oxidation of (I)

(I) when oxidised as above also gave a product with analytical and chemical properties similar to that of (V).

Reductive acetylation of (IV)

A mixture of the dye (IV) (1 g.), acetic anhydride (30 ml) and pyridine (50 ml) was refluxed with stirring. To this boiling solution, zinc dust (5 g.) was added gradually. The mixture was then refluxed for 5 hr more and filtered hot. The filtrate was acidified. The brown precipitate which separated was collected. The solution of the brown product in chloroform was chromatographed on alumina and the chromatogram was developed with the same solvent. It separated into two fractions. The less adsorbed first major brown fraction was eluted with chloroform. On concentration it gave a chocolate brown product. It crystallised from carbon tetrachloride in dark brown plates and analysed for the formula (VI). (Found : C, 79.0; H, 4.7; N, 2.6%. Calc. for C₃₇H₂₅NO₅; C, 78.9; H, 4.4; N, 2.5%). It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with light brown solution.

Reduction of (IV) with aluminium isopropoxide

The dye (IV) (1 g.) was mixed with aluminium isopropoxide (20 g.) and the mixture was refluxed for 4 hr. The mixture was cooled and treated with

hydrochloric acid, and violet precipitate (0.8 g.) was collected. Its solution in chlorobenzene was chromatographed on alumina and the chromatogram was developed with the same solvent. It separated into 4 fractions. The first least adsorbed major violet blue fraction was eluted with chlorobenzene. On concentration, it gave a violet product. Crystallisation from chlorobenzene gave violet blue needles, which analysed for the formula (VII). Found : C, 91.9; H, 4.2; N, 3.3%. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{17}N$; C, 92.3; H, 4.2; N, 3.5%. It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with a green solution. It did not react with alkaline dithionite solution. The infrared spectra of the compound did not contain any bands in the C=O region [1630-1670 cm^{-1}].

Attempted alkaline cyclisation of (I)

(I) (1 g.), powdered potassium hydroxide (4 g.) and ethylene glycol (25 ml.) were stirred at 180° for 7 hr. and the mixture was diluted with water and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The brown red product which separated was collected. The product was treated with 10% sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline solution of the product showed greenish yellow fluorescence. On acidification, 4-hydroxybenzanthrone, m.p. and m.m.p. 304°, was isolated.

A very small amount of alkali insoluble product containing 1-aminoanthraquinone, and a small amount of black dye which dyed cotton green from alkaline dithionite vat was obtained. It could not be worked up further.

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